

SYDNEY

Popular annual financial report
Fiscal Year 2021-22

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LETTER FROM THE LORD MAYOR CLOVER MOORE

We have all experienced another year impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic. The City of Sydney is recovering but we continue to face many challenges. While travel and health restrictions have been lifted, supply chain disruptions, labour shortages, rising cost of living and exceptionally wet weather have all impacted our recovery efforts and our short-term economic future. With Australia's borders reopening and international students returning, we have continued our support for this community holding networking events, career workshops and an international student employment panel. We ran a 'Your city is waiting for you' marketing campaign to revitalise the city centre, inviting residents, workers and students back into the city centre to eat, drink, dwell, see and shop. Work is largely complete on extending the boulevard from Bathurst Street to Railway Square. A new pedestrian area on Devonshire Street between Chalmers and Elizabeth Streets is already attracting applications for outdoor dining in this space. We've extended fee waivers for outdoor dining to June 2023 to support the hospitality sector and the city's economic recovery. Since we began waiving fees for outdoor dining in new spaces in November 2020, \$5.4 million in footway dining fees have been waived and 478 applications have been approved, including for 1,787sqm of reallocated road space. From January to March we ran the Sydney Summer Streets program, following a program of roving entertainment to reactivate the centre of our city and villages which began in October. Over the summer months 6 village high streets were closed to vehicles, employing 170 musicians and performers and providing space for communities to re-engage with close to 150 local businesses. It's pleasing that many of the recommendations we made were included in the Liquor Amendment Bill 2020. These reforms will enable later trading shops and businesses, more small-scale cultural activities and better sound management for nightlife and live music venues, which will be important to the post-pandemic recovery. The City of Sydney also offered new precinct activation grants, which encourage collaborative partnerships between businesses, creatives and communities that renew and transform our city centre, local precincts and neighbourhoods. I assure you we have done all we can to ensure services were consistent while we increased efforts to support the community through this challenging time. I thank our dedicated City staff, under the wonderful leadership of CEO Monica Barone, who have risen to the many serious challenges over the last 12 months, ensuring our city will not only survive Covid-19, but recover and thrive once more.

INTRODUCTION TO SYDNEY

Sydney is the capital city of the state of New South Wales, situated on the south-eastern corner of Australia. It is the country's most populous city, as well as a centre for finance, business, music, and the arts.

The area has been inhabited for the last 45000 to 50000 years, however, when the British Empire arrived in the late XVIII century, what is now Sydney only had around four to eight thousand inhabitants.

The city boasts of a number of notable tourist attractions, starting from the iconic sails of the Opera House, the beautiful Harbour Bridge, the world-famous blue ocean and sandy shores of Bondi Beach, and finally a large amount of museums such as the Royal Botanical Garden and the Art Gallery of New South Wales. Whether a person finds themselves in Sydney as a tourist, a worker, an entertainer, or to study at a university, Sydney has something to offer.

The city is inhabited by people of all ancestral backgrounds, from British and Scottish to aboriginal Eowa or Torres Strait islander peoples.

Despite being one of the most expensive cities in the world to live in, it frequently ranks as having some of the highest quality of life in the world. It is moreover ranked as an Alpha city by the GAWC, highlighting its importance in the global economy

This report has the goal of bringing together all of the relevant and important information about the city of Sydney in a digestible way.

“There’s an ease that I have living in Australia. The best things about Sydney are free: the sunshine’s free, and the harbour’s free, and the beach is free.”

~Russel Crowe

DEFINITIONS

Acronyms, financial terms, technical terms, and more

- **Balance sheet** ☞ Balance sheet is one of the fundamental financial statements and it used for financial modeling and accounting. The balance sheet displays assets on the left side and equity/liability on the right side of it as a debt. Also Balance sheet is called with other names as well like financial position or statement of net worth . The balance sheet is based on equation below :
Assets = Liabilities + Equity.
- **Income statement** ☞ shows profit and loss over a period . It used in corporate finance and accounting . The statement displays the company's revenue, costs, gross profit, selling and administrative expenses, other expenses , income, taxes paid, and net profit in a coherent and logical manner. The profit and loss will be determined by the equation below :
P/L = Revenues - expenses
- **Cash flow statement** ☞ The cash flow statement reports the cash generated and spent during a specific period of time and it is like a bridge between Balance sheet and Income statement and determines the amount of cash in and out.
- **Asset** ☞ Is a resource owns or control by corporates , institutes and etc. which has economic value and with the expectation that it will provide future value . Assets reports on the left side of the balance sheet and they are classified in 4 categories : Current / non-Current / tangible and non-tangible assets . The purpose of buying or controlling an asset is to increase the value of the company
- **Liability** ☞ when a person or a compoany ows (money, services, goods) . liability is reported on the right side of the balance sheet . Liabilities are usually owed or borrowed and has to pay off in the future .
- **Equity** ☞ Usually refers to the shareholder's equity for private companies . Equity represents the value that would be returned to a company's shareholders if all of the assets were liquidated and all of the company's debts were paid off. Equity will be found on the right side of the balance sheet .
- **Revenues** ☞ is the money that brought to the company by the business activities .the value/ revenue is considered when the goods or service delivered to the costumer . In some certain cases revenue is considered even though cash has not been received also it will be find in income statement.
- **Expenses** ☞ is the cost of operation that company does to generate revenues and it will be find in income statement .
- **PPE (property , plant and equipment)** ☞ physical or tangible assets that are long-term assets and have a life of more than one year

DEFINITIONS

Acronyms, financial terms, technical terms, and more

- **Cash** ☞ is a currency that can be used for goods and services . the value of asset also can be easily converted to cash . In corporate terms it is usually bank accounts , securities such as bonds and banker's acceptance .
- **Depreciation/Amortization** ☞ are two methods to estimate the value of tangible/intangible assets over the time . cost of asset divided by the useful life gives us depreciation amount.
- **Inventory** ☞ raw materials are used for producing products and also finished goods that are ready for sale . Inventory is considered one of the most important assets because of the turnover of inventory and it is the primary source of the revenue generation . There are 3 types of the inventory : raw materials , work-in progress and finished products . it is displayed in balance sheet as a current asset of the company
- **Interest** ☞ Interest is the monetary charge for borrowing money. Interest usually considered as simple interest
- **Debt** ☞ borrower owes some money to the lender. Usually it is a huge amount of money that borrower cannot afford to use for purchases . Debt has to be paid back unless a debt is forgiven by the lender.
- **Diploma** ☞ A diploma is a document awarded by an educational institution (such as a college or university) to declare the recipient has graduated by successfully completing their courses of studies. This word historically comes from the document of diplomacy.
- **Bachelor degree** ☞ a degree that is given to a student by a college or university usually after 4 years of study.
- **Chief financial officer** (CFO) ☞ an officer who is assigned for making decisions of finances and projects for a company.
- **Chief operator officer** (COO) ☞ An executive who is in charge of daily operations of the organization.
- **Aboriginals** ☞ no known others preceding in occupancy of a particular region.
- **Indigenous** ☞ is not only native but which has never been introduced or brought from elsewhere.
- **Native** ☞ people who are local or born there

GENERAL DATA AND CONTEXT

Sydney is the capital of the State of New South Wales, situated in the South-eastern part of Australia. It is the largest city in the country and allocated in the strategic positions and it is one of the most important ports in the South Pacific .

Area City of Sydney, 10.3 square miles (26.7 square km); Greater Sydney Statistical Area, 4,790 square miles (12,406 square km).

You will find some demo-graphs about the population size below :

Gender distribution and population size

Gender distribution in percentage

women

Men

- the sex ratio in Sydney is 98.9 male for 100 female in year 2022

Year	Population	Growth rate
2018	4,792,000	1.78%
2019	4,859,000	1.40%
2020	4,926,000	1.38%
2021	4,992,000	1.34%
2022	5,057,000	1.30%

CONTEXTUAL ACTIVITIES

Main business in Sydney

The main sectors which Greater Sydney operates are services, ICT and creative industries.

The other types of businesses also the state operates are insurance services, professional, scientific and technical services, and information media and telecommunications industries, as well as the tourism-related accommodation and food services, and arts and recreation services industries.

Average weekly income

	2022	2021	2021 to 2022 (change%)
Men	\$1,425	\$1,380	3.3%
Women	\$1,094	\$1,030	6.2%
Total	\$1,250	\$1,200	4.2%

Median weekly earnings for women increased with the faster rate than men over the past 5 years, especially the number of women working full-time has been increased.

CONTEXTUAL ACTIVITIES

Participation in the labor force

	Jun-2022	Jul-2022	Monthly change	Monthly change (%)	Yearly change	Yearly change (%)
Seasonally adjusted						
Employed people	13,599,300	13,558,400	-40,900	-0.3%	398,500	3.0%
Unemployed people	493,900	473,600	-20,200	-4.1%	-167,600	-26.1%
Unemployment rate	3.5%	3.4%	-0.1 pts	na	-1.3 pts	na
Underemployment rate	6.1%	6.0%	-0.1 pts	na	-2.3 pts	na
Participation rate	66.8%	66.4%	-0.3 pts	na	0.4 pts	na
Monthly hours worked in all jobs	1,855 million	1,840 million	-16 million	-0.8%	61 million	3.4%

- Unemployment rate has been decreased and employment rate has been increased in 2022 compared to year 2021.
- 71% of Men and 50% of women between age 15-75 are fully engaged in working and studying.

Age distribution of Sydney 2022

EDUCATION AND AWARDS

Education level distribution table

Level of highest educational attainment <i>People aged 15 years and over</i>	Greater Sydney	%
Bachelor Degree level and above	1,423,358	33.3
Advanced Diploma and Diploma level	412,740	9.7
Certificate level IV	116,490	2.7
Certificate level III	389,224	9.1
Year 12	679,878	15.9
Year 11	125,161	2.9
Year 10	359,130	8.4
Certificate level II	2,110	0.0
Certificate level I	429	0.0
Year 9 or below	266,766	6.3
Inadequately described	119,016	2.8
No educational attainment	55,835	1.3
Not stated	317,095	7.4

Universities of Sydney in 2022

There are 6 main universities in Sydney that are listed below :

- Australian Catholic University
- Macquarie University
- University of New South Wales
- University of Sydney
- University of Technology Sydney
- Western Sydney University

Awards

- Sydney Opera House in 2007
- Sydney Film Festival
- Sydney Harbour Bridge
- Sydney's Beaches:
- Sydney Writers' Festival
- Australian Museum
- Sydney's Public Transport
- Sydney's Culinary Scene

POPULATION DATA

Total population of Sydney 2022

5,297,089

Total population of Greater Sydney 2022

- Australian born
- Overseas born

Total distribution of Native and Non-natives population in Greater Sydney 2022

Life expectancy at birth

Total Fertility rate	1,66
Life Expectancy at birth- Male	81,1
Life Expectancy at birth- female	85,2

Distribution of international habitants in Greater Sydney 2022

Ranking and positioning

Quality life Index of Sydney 2022

Quality of life Index	184.5
Purchasing power Index	114.6
Safety Index	66.2
Health care Index	78.6
Cost of living Index	76.6
Property price to income ratio	10.6
Traffic commute time Index	43.4
Pollution Index	27.3
Climate Index	97.1

Sydney position in the different ranking lists 2022:

- In year 2022 only one cities of Australia could make it to the list of best social cities ranking which is Sydney ranked in 46th place , dropped sharply from 16th place in 2021 .
- Sydney Ranked 62nd in the world for graduate employability
- Sydney Ranked 33rd place in the Arcadis Sustainable Cities Index
- Sydney Index for the most livable cities in the world is 97.4 which put Sydney in the 4th place after Vienna , Copenhagen and Melbourne
- After Melbourne ,Sydney is the largest city in Austrailia and ranked in the 2nd place

Ranking and positioning

Sydney position in the digital/smart cities ranking list :

According to the Digital cities index 2022 , Sydney is in the top 10 digital cities . 4 of the cities are in Europe,4 of them in pacific Asia and 2 of them in the US .Sydney is located in the 7th grade of the top smart cities in world 2022 .

1	Copenhagen	81.5	16	Berlin	68.2
2	Amsterdam	74.6	17	Hong Kong	68.0
3	Beijing	73.7	18	Dubai	63.8
=4	London	73.6	19	Madrid	63.2
=4	Seoul	73.6	20	Tokyo	63.0
6	New York	73.3	21	Rome	61.2
7	Sydney	72.6	22	Auckland	60.1
8	Singapore	71.4	23	Kuala Lumpur	58.2
9	Washington DC	71.2	24	São Paulo	50.7
10	Paris	70.2	25	Bangkok	49.1
=11	Toronto	70.1	26	Buenos Aires	45.1
=11	Zurich	70.1	27	Jakarta	43.5
13	Barcelona	69.7	28	Mexico City	42.6
14	Frankfurt	69.1	29	New Delhi	40.3

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION GROUP

Organisational chart of the Sydney Government

Committees

The city of Sydney's administration is split into a number of committees, each with 3 members:

- Corporate, Finance, Properties and Tenders Committee
- Cultural and Community Committee
- Environment Committee
- Transport Heritage and Planning Committee
- Central Sydney Planning Committee
- Local Pedestrian, Cycling and Traffic Calming Committee

City services

The city of Sydney provides many services:

- Waste & recycling
- Rates
- Pets & animals
- Property & tree maintenance
- Child care & family services
- Transport & parking
- Construction, certification and development
- Public domain works
- Construction permits & approvals
- Hoardings & temporary structure approvals
- Facility bookings & outdoor events

SYDNEY

Land use

BY THE NUMBERS

2022 Population
218,096

Defense service
Regular defense service 1,571
Reserves defense service 1,357

City employees
141,464

Gross regional product
141.04 billion
% of the state's GSP
(gross state product)
21.32%

Sydney Area
26.7
square km

TRANSPORTATION
Private car 14.1%
Public transport(train) 9.4%
Bike/walked 10.8%
worked at home 52.3%

INCOME STATEMENT

for the year ended 30 june 2022

Item	2022	2021	note
Income from continuing operations			
Rates & annual charges	376,728	369,374	B2-1
User charges & fees	95,513	106,687	B2-2
Other revenue	23,215	75,790	B2-3
Grants & contributions for operating purposes	19,223	24,071	B2-4
Grants & contributions for capital purposes	68,983	144,701	B2-4
Interest & investment income	5,189	5,501	B2-5
Other income	76,621	100,971	B2-6
Net gain from the disposal of assets	11,029	20,740	B4-1
Total income from continuing operations	676,501	847,835	
Expenses from continuing operations			
Employee benefits and on-costs	238,234	231,358	B3-1
Materials & services	225,485	251,715	B3-2
Borrowing costs	228	254	B3-3

INCOME STATEMENT

for the year ended 30 June 2022

Item	2022	2021	note
Depreciation, amortisation and impairment of non-financial assets	108,153	122,011	B3-4
Other expenses	39,451	46,871	B3-5
Total expense from continuing operations	611,551	652,209	
Operating result from continuing operations	64,950	195,626	
Net operating result for the year attributable to Council	64,950	195,626	
Net operating result for the year before grants and contributions provided for capital purposes	(4,033)	50,925	

The above Income Statement should be read in conjunction with the accompanying notes.

STATEMENT OF COMPREHENSIVE INCOME

for the year ended 30 June 2022

Item	2022	2021	note
Net operating result for the year – from Income Statement	64,950	195,626	
Other comprehensive income			
Amounts which will not be reclassified subsequently to the operating result			
Gain (loss) on revaluation of infrastructure, property, plant and equipment	235,289	(189,338)	C1-8
Movement in Trust Assets reserve - Crown land revaluation	-	(1,855,827)	C1-8
Total items which will not be reclassified subsequently to the operating result	235,289	(2,045,165)	
Total comprehensive income for the year attributable to Council	300,239	(1,849,539)	

The above Statement of Comprehensive Income should be read in conjunction with the accompanying notes.

(1) In 2020/21, Council updated its valuation methodology in respect of Crown and Community Land, incorporating input from external valuers (previously generalised valuation information from the Valuer General was utilised in valuations of these classes).

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

for the year ended 30 june 2022

ASSET	2022	2021	note
Current assets			
Cash and cash equivalents	63,790	51,051	C1-1
Investments	483,300	417,600	C1-2
Receivables	45,633	57,858	C1-4
Inventories	989	989	C1-5
Contract assets	23,560	17,195	C1-6
Other	7,828	6,997	C1-11
Non-current assets classified as 'held for sale'	26,837	35,599	C1-7
Total current assets	651,937	587,289	

1) while inventories remain the same as the previous year, total current assets has increased due to the increased of liquidity and investments.

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

for the year ended 30 june 2022

ASSET	2022	2021	note
Non-current assets			
Investments	167,950	186,604	C1-2
Receivables	22,735	31,248	C1-4
Infrastructure, property, plant and equipment (IPPE)	11,773,741	11,470,866	C1-8
Investment property	399,172	384,259	C1-9
Intangible assets	36,144	52,550	C1-10
Right of use assets	10,961	12,551	C2-1
Other	98	112	C1-11
Total non-current assets	12,410,801	12,138,190	
Total assets	13,062,738	12,725,479	

The above Statement of Financial Position should be read in conjunction with the accompanying notes.

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

LIABILITIES	2022	2021	note
Current liabilities			
Payables	104,375	104,047	C3-1
Contract liabilities	30,040	27,467	C3-2
Lease liabilities	234	203	C2-1
Employee benefit provisions	61,279	63,717	C3-4
Provisions	19,798	9,927	C3-5
Total current liabilities	215,726	205,361	
Non-current liabilities			
Contract liabilities	70,437	46,070	C3-2
Lease liabilities	11,522	12,960	C2-1
Employee benefit provisions	4,142	5,104	C3-4
Provisions	27,266	22,578	C3-5

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

for the year ended 30 June 2022

LIABILITIES	2022	2021	note
Total non-current liabilities	113,367	86,712	
Total liabilities	329,093	292,073	
Net assets	12,733,645	12,433,406	
EQUITY			
Accumulated surplus	4,257,500	4,192,250	
IPPE revaluation reserve	5,479,514	5,227,265	C4-1
Trust Assets Reserve	2,996,631	3,013,891	C4-1
Total equity	12,733,645	12,433,406	

Each year, individual local governments across NSW are required to present a set of audited financial statements. In accordance with Section 418 (3) of the Local Government Act, 1993, City of Sydney advises that the Ordinary Council Meeting to be held on 21 November 2022 will include the presentation of the audited Financial Reports and the Auditors Reports for the financial year ending 30 June 2022.

The statements set out the financial performance, financial position and cash flows of the council for the financial year ending 30 June 2022. They also contain explanatory notes for the major components of income and expenditure and the financial position of assets and liabilities.

The above Statement of Financial Position should be read in conjunction with the accompanying notes. Contents for the notes to the Financial Statements for the year ended 30 June 2022, you can find them in this link

<https://www.cityofsydney.nsw.gov.au/surveys-case-studies-reports/annual-report#:~:text=Financial%20statements%202021/22>

SUMMARY OF FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Income Statement	2022	2021
Total Income from Continuing Operations	676,501	847,835
Total Expenses from Continuing Operations	611,551	652,209
Operating Result from Continuing Operations	64,950	195,626
Net Operating Result for the year	64,950	195,626
Net Operating Result before Capital Grants & Contributions	(4,033)	50,925

Balance Sheet		
Total Current Assets	651,937	587,289
Total Current Liabilities	(215,726)	(205,361)
Total Non-Current Assets	12,410,801	12,138,190
Total Non-Current Liabilities	(113,367)	(86,712)
Total Equity	12,733,645	12,433,406

Other Financial Information		
Operating Performance Ratio (excl. non-recurrent capital expenses) (%)	(2.41%)	5.14%
Operating Performance Ratio (%)	(4.84%)	(1.25%)
Own Source Operating Revenue Ratio (%)	86.46%	78.58%
Unrestricted Current Ratio	4.17 : 1	3.95 : 1
Unrestricted Current Ratio (less External & Internal Restrictions)	2.95 : 1	3.14 : 1
Debt Service Ratio (%)	177.84%	258.47%
Rates & Annual Charges Outstanding Ratio (%)	1.96%	2.16%
Cash Expense Cover Ratio (months)	12.48	10.84

DESCRIPTION OF MAJOR POLICIES

The Sydney Community Strategic Plan

Public perception

The biggest opportunities for positive change are:

- 52%**
Cost of living
- 17%**
Health and well-being services
- 9%**
Environment

58%
Of citizens love where they live

34%
of citizens consider New South Wales a center for technology

Ten major policy directions Sydney Community Strategic Plan

Responsible governance and stewardship	Leading in environmental performance	Public places for all	Design excellence and sustainable development	Developing a city for walking, cycling, and public transport
An equitable and inclusive city	Resilient and diverse communities	A thriving cultural and creative life	A transformed and innovative economy	Housing for all

Six guiding principles of Sydney Policy

We are accountable to the voices and elevate the knowledge and cultures of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples

The city of Sydney strives to reflect the needs and wants of its aboriginal and Torres Strait community. The administration will work to authentically strengthen relationships and build communities

We respond to the climate emergency

The city responds to the climate emergency and takes it into account with every single policy that is enacted. Bold steps are being taken and will be taken to reach the goal of a net-zero and regenerative economy in 2050. Sydney promotes change in transportation, power generation, and water use, as well as in building an equitable society where nobody is left behind.

We build the resilience of our society and economy

Partnerships between communities, government, and businesses strengthen the city. The city aims to build resilience in the economy and in policy in order to be able to respond to, adapt, and recover from any shock or systemic stress that may arise in the future. Among these stressors are pressure on the health service and inequality.

Our communities are engaged in the governance of their city

The City of Sydney is led by a democratic government where people can influence decisions without prejudice of age, wealth, or occupation. People are encouraged to be effective and connected community builders and to engage with local leaders in order to make Sydney a better place for everyone.

We lead through stewardship and collaboration

The city of Sydney will facilitate social harmony and inclusion while leading the economy into the future. As steward of the city, the administration makes sure to take into account the full impact of each one of its policies on all stakeholders, as well as collaborating with the state and national governments to achieve goals.

Our organisation is governed responsibly and sustainably

Responsibility is taken to balance everyone's needs and interests in the present and future. This policy ensures that the investments made today are financially sustainable for both the current generation and the future ones. Fairness and equity, as well as ethics, transparency, accountability, and community involvement underpin all choices made by the Sydney government.

Main policies

Environmental

Sydney aims to be a leading player in environmental policy. With Australia's bureau of Meteorology projecting a temperature rise of 4.4°C for the country, the environmental performance of the city will be a key issue in the following years. The main objectives of these policies are reaching net zero by 2035, creating a green city, better management of water resources, creating a circular economy, and finally collaborating with businesses and citizens to reduce their emissions.

How the outcomes are measured

Results related to environmental policies are measured according to the GPC-4 international benchmark, as well as city-specific measures such as green coverage, water consumption per person, and the percentage of residential waste being recycled.

Housing

With over 80% of citizens concerned with the rising housing costs in the Sydney area, housing is a key priority by the administration. Under the city's "Housing for all" policy direction, Sydney aims to end homelessness, guarantee a supply of quality housing, a good mix of different housing options in each neighbourhood, as well as guaranteeing that Torres Strait Islanders and aboriginal people have culturally appropriate housing.

How the outcomes are measured

Housing for all policies measure results by using several tools: regular surveys, percentage of social housing, percentage of affordable housing and its cost, number of private and non-private dwellings, and data from community and housing providers. The main common denominators between these data sources are the City of Sydney's Housing Audit and the ABS Census, taken yearly and every five years respectively.

Equity

The city is a centre of tech and business, however, research shows that there are considerable inequalities between Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders communities. The main goals are strengthening ties to these communities, making sure everyone feels included and welcomed, ensuring everyone benefits from growth, engaging communities, ensuring communities have the means to participate in a digital life, equitable access to education, and lastly giving everyone access to affordable and nutritious food.

How the outcomes are measured

Equity policies results are mainly qualitative, and they are measured through community wellbeing indicators. These indicators include satisfaction surveys, financial security, participation in decision making, internet access, satisfaction with the education system, and percentage of people who had trouble buying food

Dissemination plan

Objectives

This report aims to provide a large number of people with crucial information about how the city of Sydney conducts its business, as well as what are its main characteristics, trends, policies, and structures.

Audience

Any relevant stakeholder of any age, nationality, and background, as well as anyone that might simply be interested in learning how the City of Sydney is run and managed.

Situation

The broader context of this research begins from the need to have a throughout understanding of the complex reality that is the City of Sydney and its related metropolitan area.

Messaging

The dissemination of this research will focus on spreading the message that, by giving the people a good understanding of current city affairs, better decisions can be made on a personal, community, and political level. Thus, by spreading this research, the City of Sydney can be made a better place thanks to everyone's cooperation.

Strategy

The overarching dissemination strategy focuses on young people, mainly the ones that have, with time, become dissatisfied and apathetic to the current political climate.

Tactics

The main tactics used will include social media, promoting community meetings and social gatherings related to the contents of this research. Lastly, cooperation and groupwork related to this research will be emphasised.

Evaluation

Our evaluation recommendation consists of four surveys distributed through social media, at 6 months intervals, in order to measure the impact on communities.

Methodological Notes

Standards

The financial statements are prepared in accordance with

- The Local Government Act 1993 and the regulations made thereunder,
- The Australian Accounting Standards and other pronouncements of the Australian Accounting Standards Board,
- The Local Government Code of Accounting Practice and Financial Reporting.

The measurement of policy results occurs in accordance with the 17 SDGs and related standards outlined by the UN and the OECD, where applicable.

The financial statements of the Council of the City of Sydney have been audited (the Council), which comprise the Statement by Councillors and Management, the Income Statement and Statement of Comprehensive Income for the year ended 30 June 2022, the Statement of Financial Position as at 30 June 2022, the Statement of Changes in Equity and Statement of Cash Flows for the year then ended and notes comprising a summary of significant accounting policies and other explanatory information.

Australian Government

Australian Accounting
Standards Board

Division of work

Yuhang Zheng

- Mayor's letter
- Consolidated Financial Statements
- Conclusion

Yasaman Mokhtari Azad

- Definitions
- General Data and context
- Rankings and positioning
- Conclusion

Andrea Sapei

- Introduction
- Description of Major Policies
- Dissemination Plan
- Methodological Notes
- Public Administration Group
- Conclusion

Conclusion

This report provides an overview of the City of Sydney for the fiscal year 2021-22. It covers key topics such as the city's recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic, its demographic data, key policies, and financial statements.

- A letter from the Lord Mayor, Clover Moore, talks about the challenges and recovery efforts in the city due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Support for the community, especially international students, has been continuous.
- Sydney, the capital of New South Wales, stands as the most populous city in Australia and is well known for its diverse culture and high quality of life.
- The General Data section details the city's demographic data, including gender distribution, population size, and age distribution. It also houses details about community participation in the labor force.
- Major policies in Sydney are directed at objectives such as environmental sustainability, housing affordability, and addressing inequality. These policies aim to improve the quality of life for all residents.
- The report also presents the financial statements for the fiscal year ended on June 30th 2022, providing insights into the city's financial position.
- The methodological notes section explains the standards used for preparing the financial statements and the report, as well as the division of work among the team.

This work was completed as part of the Public Management course at the School of Advanced Studies (SAA), University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia. The elements presented in this assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia, and Davide Calandra.

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